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Additional Information

Considering Population Variability of Electrophysiological Models Improves the *In Silico* Assessment of Drug-Induced Torsadogenic Risk

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9 **Keywords:** in-silico, proarrhythmic-risk, Torsade de Pointes, cardiac safety, population
10 of models.

11 **Abstract**

12 *Background and Objective:* *In silico* tools are known to aid in drug cardiotoxicity
13 assessment. However, computational models do not usually consider electrophysiological
14 variability, which may be crucial when predicting rare adverse events such as drug-
15 induced Torsade de Pointes (TdP). In addition, classification tools are usually binary and
16 are not validated using an external data set. Here we analyze the role of incorporating
17 electrophysiological variability in the prediction of drug-induced arrhythmogenic-risk,
18 using a ternary classification and two external validation datasets.

19 *Methods:* The effects of the 12 training CiPA drugs were simulated at three different
20 concentrations using a single baseline model and an electrophysiologically calibrated

21 population of models. 9 biomarkers related with action potential (AP), calcium dynamics
22 and net charge were measured for each simulated concentration. These biomarkers were
23 used to build ternary classifiers based on Support Vector Machines (SVM) methodology.
24 Classifiers were validated using two external drug sets: the 16 validation CiPA drugs and
25 81 drugs from CredibleMeds database.

26 *Results:* Population of models allowed to obtain different AP responses under the same
27 pharmacological intervention and improve the prediction of drug-induced TdP with
28 respect to the baseline model. The classification tools based on population of models
29 achieve an accuracy higher than 0.8 and a mean classification error (MCE) lower than 0.3
30 for both validation drug sets and for the two electrophysiological action potential models
31 studied (Tomek et al. 2020 and a modified version of O'Hara et al. 2011). In addition,
32 simulations with population of models allowed the identification of individuals with
33 lower conductances of I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{NaK} and higher conductances of I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{NCX} ,
34 which are more prone to develop TdP.

35 *Conclusions:* The methodology presented here provides new opportunities to assess drug-
36 induced TdP-risk, taking into account electrophysiological variability and may be helpful
37 to improve current cardiac safety screening methods.

38 **1 Introduction**

39 Drug-induced Torsade de Pointes (TdP) is a special form of polymorphic ventricular
40 tachycardia. It is one of the most frightening adverse drug reactions because it can
41 precipitate ventricular fibrillation and cause sudden death. Although it is a rare adverse
42 event, accounting for less than one case out of 100,000 exposures, several compounds,
43 including antidepressants, pain medications, antihistamines, etc., have been withdrawn
44 from the market because of their risk of inducing TdP [1,2]. Over the last years, new

45 strategies for the assessment of drug induced TdP-risk have been proposed with the aim
46 of complementing and improving current regulatory guidelines [3]. One remarkable
47 example is the Comprehensive In Vitro Proarrhythmia Assay (CiPA) initiative, which
48 considers that *in silico* simulations of proarrhythmic effects for different compounds are
49 essential to improve arrhythmogenicity prediction.

50 Most of the mathematical and biophysical cardiac models used in *in silico* studies
51 typically represent the average behavior of a group of cells characterized experimentally.
52 Therefore, these models do not take into account electrophysiological variability [4].
53 However, it is well-known that identical pharmacological interventions produce different
54 responses between individuals. When taking a certain drug, most of the individuals may
55 not suffer any side effects while some of them may undergo TdP. For this reason,
56 accounting for electrophysiological variability may help better estimate drug-induced
57 proarrhythmicity. A useful strategy to account for variability in *in silico* models are
58 population of models [5,6]. Briefly, to build a population of models, a certain number of
59 model parameters are randomly varied, generally the conductance of different ion
60 channels, thus creating a variety of cellular behaviors.

61 Other limitations of some *in silico* classifications tools that have been published are
62 that: i) they are usually based on two-class categorization systems (TdP+ and TdP-), and
63 ii) they use cross-validation methods (e.g., leave-one-out-cross-validation), in which the
64 data used to train the model are also used to validate the model. The White Paper
65 published by Li and colleagues [7] recommends the use of a three-class system (high-
66 risk, intermediate-risk, and low-risk), which represents a compromise between
67 quantitative and qualitative risk assessment. First non-binary *in silico* drug induced TdP-
68 risk classifier was published by Mirams and colleagues[8] in 2011, but since then few
69 non-binary pro-arrhythmic classifiers have been proposed. Furthermore, the White Paper

70 also stresses that a validation of the tool with a “hidden” test data set, i.e. data not used
71 during the training phase, provides higher confidence on the performance of the tool. To
72 the best of our knowledge, there are only two studies that follow these two principles
73 published to date: a publication by Li and co-workers [9], which uses the “torsade metric
74 score” to classify 16 drugs according to their TdP-risk; and a work by Yoo and
75 collaborators [10], which proposes an artificial neural network using nine features related
76 with charge, action potential, and calcium transient morphology.

77 The aim of this study is to analyze the role of incorporating electrophysiological
78 variability in the prediction of drug-induced arrhythmogenic-risk. Specifically, the effects
79 of the 12 training CiPA drugs are simulated on a single baseline model and on an
80 electrophysiologically calibrated population of models. Ternary classifiers are built using
81 biomarkers extracted from the simulations of these 12 drugs and are validated with the
82 result from the simulations of 2 drugs datasets: one containing the 16 validation CiPA
83 drugs and the other containing 81 drugs from CredibleMeds. In addition, to evaluate the
84 influence of the action potential model, the same strategy was performed using two
85 different action potential models.

86 **2 Materials and Methods**

87 **2.1 *In Silico* population of models**

88 The electrophysiological characteristics of human ventricular cells were simulated
89 taking as reference two of the latest human endocardial ventricular action potential (AP)
90 models: the model published by Tomek and colleagues [11] (TorORd) with the dynamic
91 intracellular chloride and a modified version of the widely used AP model developed by
92 O’Hara’s group [12] (ORdmD). The modifications applied to the O’Hara et al. model are
93 described in a previous study [13]. In short, model modifications include the modulation
94 of six channel conductances (I_{Kr} multiplied by a factor of 1.119, I_{Ks} by 1.648, I_{K1} by 1.414,

95 I_{CaL} by 1.018, I_{NaL} by 2.274, and I_{Na} by 0.4) and a reformulation of the activation and
96 inactivation gates of I_{Na} . These modifications were designed to better reproduce
97 experimental data on drug effects.

98 To account for electrophysiological variability, two populations of models were built
99 using the aforementioned models as a template. The methodology for constructing the
100 population was the same for both models. First, an initial population of 1,000 models was
101 generated. These models were obtained by randomly and simultaneously modifying the
102 conductances of the ionic currents of the AP model (15 parameters in the case of ORdmD
103 and 17 in the case of TorORd). These scale factors modifying the channel conductances
104 were randomly sampled from a normal distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation
105 0.2, thus assuring that the majority of the population (>99%) was in a range between
106 $\pm 60\%$ with respect to the baseline model. To model non-diseased healthy
107 cardiomyocytes, the results of previous modelling studies [14,15] suggest that a variation
108 bigger than $\pm 50\%$ in conductance values (from the value of the parameter in the baseline
109 model) would allow substantial variability.

110 After running the simulations using the initial populations in control conditions, a
111 calibration was performed. Models with electrophysiological biomarkers not fulfilling the
112 calibration requirements were discarded. Plausible electrophysiological properties were
113 defined according to acceptable ranges, found in the literature, for 15 characteristics
114 related to AP duration, amplitude of membrane potential, and calcium dynamics
115 [6,12,16–20]. Limits of acceptance for the 15 electrophysiological properties considered
116 are shown in **Table 1**. Simulations were run at 37°C and at the following extracellular
117 concentrations: $[Na^+]=140$ nM, $[Ca^{2+}]=1.8$ nM and $[K^+]=5.4$ nM in order to replicate the
118 experimental conditions of the in vitro experiments.

119 **Table 1.** Action Potential and Ca²⁺-related biomarkers ranges used to calibrate the control
 120 population of human ventricular AP *in silico* models.

Biomarker	Min Value	Max Value
APD40 (ms) [6]	85	320
APD50 (ms) [6]	110	350
APD90 (ms) [6]	180	440
Tri 90-40 (ms) [6,12]	50	150
dV/dt (mV/ms) [12]	150	1000
Vpeak (mV) [6,12]	10	55
RMP (mV) [6,12]	-95	-80
CTD50 (ms) [20]	120	420
CTD90 (ms) [20]	220	785
Ca²⁺ syst (μM) [17]	0.262	2.23
Ca²⁺ diast (μM) [17]	--	0.40
Na⁺ (mM) [19]	--	39.27
ΔAPD90 (%) under 90% I_{Ks} [12]	-54.4	62
ΔAPD90 (%) under 70% I_{Kr} [18]	32.25	91.94
ΔAPD90 (%) under 50% I_{K1} [16]	-5.26	14.86

121 After calibration, 810 models of the TorORd-based population and 860 models of the
 122 ORdmD-based population presented a plausible electrophysiological behavior according
 123 to experimental data. AP and calcium transient traces of the TorORd-based population
 124 are shown in **Figure 2**. As shown in the Figure the population of models presents
 125 electrophysiological variability. For example, the APD₉₀ of the baseline model yields
 126 272.25 ms, and the population of models presents APD_{90s} varying between 185.78 and
 127 406.3 ms. This electrophysiological variability can also be observed in calcium dynamics,
 128 where systolic [Ca²⁺] varies between 0.263 μM and 1.195 μM. The ORdmD population
 129 is shown in the **Supplementary Material, Figure S1**. Distributions of the biomarkers
 130 used for calibration across each population of models (TorORd and ORdmD) are
 131 represented in **Figure S2 and S3**.

132
 133 **Figure 1.** Action potentials (A) and calcium transient (B) traces of the calibrated
 134 population (810 models). Solid black lines represent TorORd baseline model.

135 2.2 Drug Data Set and Drug Effect Simulation

136 Drug effects on the AP were simulated via the simple pore block model. Thus, the block
 137 produced on each current was simulated by scaling the channel's maximal conductance
 138 (g_i). This scaling factor was calculated using the standard Hill equation (eq. 1):

$$g_{i,drug} = g_i \left[1 + \left(\frac{D}{IC_{50,i}} \right)^h \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

139 where $g_{i,drug}$ is the maximal conductance of channel i in the presence of the drug, D
 140 is the drug concentration, $IC_{50,i}$ is the half-maximal response dose for that drug and
 141 current through channel i and h is the Hill coefficient, which indicates the number of
 142 molecules of drug that are assumed to be sufficient to block one ion channel.

143 In this work we considered drug effects on the seven ionic currents selected by the Ion
 144 Channel Working Group of the CiPA initiative [21]. These currents play the most
 145 important role in the generation of the AP and cardiac arrhythmias (I_{Na} , I_{NaL} , I_{Kr} , I_{to} , I_{CaL} ,
 146 I_{K1} , and I_{Ks}).

147 Here, we study and assess the proarrhythmic-risk of the 28 CiPA drugs [21] and an
148 extra set of 81 drugs. The IC_{50} values, Hill coefficients (h) and human effective free
149 therapeutic plasma concentrations (EFTPC) for each drug were obtained following the
150 methodology described in previous studies [13,22]. In summary, for each value data were
151 collected from public databases and from the scientific literature and the median value
152 (i.e., the center of the distribution of all published data) was selected. Therefore, previous
153 drug datasets [13,22] were reviewed and updated with recently published data. The
154 EFTPC, IC_{50} , and Hill coefficient values for the 109 drugs are listed in the
155 **Supplementary Material, Table S1.**

156 Each drug was simulated at three different concentrations: at the EFTPC, at 5 times
157 EFTPC, and at 10 times EFTPC. All simulations were carried out with a basic cycle length
158 (BCL) of 1000 ms and a stimulus of 1.5-fold the diastolic threshold amplitude and a
159 duration of 0.5 ms. The measurements of the biomarkers were done after 500 beats
160 starting from control -no drug- initial values. Differences between biomarkers measured
161 on two consecutive beats at this point was less than 0.5%. At each concentration, 9
162 biomarkers related to TdP-induction risk were measured: action potential duration at 90%
163 repolarization (APD90), triangulation 90-30, triangulation 90-50, net charge throughout
164 the AP (qNet) [23], systolic and diastolic intracellular calcium concentration, calcium
165 transient duration at 90% and 50% repolarization (CTD90 and CTD50), and the
166 electromechanical window (EMw), defined as CTD90-APD90 [24].

167 A repolarization abnormality was defined as either: i) an Early After Depolarization
168 (EADs), i.e. any event with a positive voltage gradient ($dV/dt > 0$ mV/ms) after 100 ms
169 from the beginning of the AP; ii) a repolarization failure, i.e. the membrane voltage at the
170 end of the beat being higher than resting membrane voltage ($V_m > -40$ mV); or iii) any

171 event with a positive calcium transient gradient ($dCa^{2+}/dt > 0$ nM/ms) after 300 ms from
172 the beginning of the AP.

173 **2.3 Drug-Induced TdP-Risk Assessment**

174 For the assessment of drug-induced TdP-risk we followed the same methodology for
175 both AP models (ORdmD and TorORd). First, the 12 training CiPA drugs were simulated
176 at three different concentrations using both: the baseline model and the population of
177 models. As mentioned before, at each concentration, 9 biomarkers were measured,
178 therefore the drug effect was characterized by 27 parameters in each model. In the case
179 that a repolarization abnormality occurred during the last 3 beats, none of the biomarkers
180 was measured and it was considered that the drug, for that specific model, poses high risk
181 of inducing TdP.

182 Using these 27 biomarkers as input, two ternary classifiers (high-risk, intermediate-
183 risk, and low-risk) were built: one for the baseline model and the other one for the
184 population of models. In both cases, a ternary Support Vector Machines (SVM) model
185 with a 1/3 hold out cross-validation was trained. For the training phase only the
186 simulations of the 12 training CiPA drugs were used. For the SVM hyperparameters
187 optimization, leave-p-out cross-validation (being p equal to a third of all the training
188 simulations) was performed with 50 bootstrap repetitions, i.e., the training phase was
189 repeated 50 times to avoid the influence of data partitioning. For the training of the
190 classifier using the population of models, the cross-validation was applied using all the
191 drugs on all models of the population (i.e. the number of training points was: 8 drugs*
192 number of models of the population).

193 In the case of the population of models, for each drug, the percentage of models or
194 individuals that are classified as high, as intermediate, or as low-risk was calculated. Next,

195 to determine the risk category of the drug, two logistic regression (one for high-vs.-no
 196 high-risk prediction and other for low-vs.-no low-risk prediction) was applied on these
 197 percentages. This way, the classification tool built using the population of models yields
 198 the TdP-risk category of the drug, associated with the percentage of models in each
 199 category.

200 **Figure 2** shows a schematic representation of the overall method for constructing the
 201 baseline model-based classifier (**Figure 2A**) and the population of models-based
 202 classifier (**Figure 2B**)

203
 204 **Figure 2.** Schematic representation of the overall method to build the classifiers. (A)
 205 Baseline model-based classifier: the 12 CiPA training drug effects were simulated in the
 206 baseline model, then a SVM with 4 drugs held out was trained. (B) Population of models-
 207 based classifier: the 12 CiPA training drug effects were simulated in the population of
 208 models and a SVM with 4 drugs held out was trained. The percentage of that are classified
 209 as high, as intermediate, or as low-risk was used as input of a logistic regression model
 210 to determine the overall risk category of the drug. Both classification tools were tested
 211 with two external datasets.

212 The TdP-risk classifiers were built and evaluated using the Statistics and Machine
 213 Learning Toolbox from MATLAB, version R2021b. The SVM kernels and
 214 hyperparameters were tuned using the Bayesian Optimization algorithm. We tested three

215 kernel functions: Gaussian, linear and polynomial. The margin C was selected from the
216 range $[10^{-4}, 10^4]$. For the Gaussian kernel, the gamma parameter tested ranged from $[10^{-4},$
217 $10^4]$. The polynomial order evaluated ranged from [2, 5]. The final SVM configuration
218 for the different classifiers presented in this work are reported in **Table S4**.

219 For visual interpretation of the classification results in the population, we defined a
220 TdP-score. The TdP-score was calculated as the value of the high-vs.-no high-risk
221 regression model minus the value of the low-vs.-no low-risk regression model. This score
222 was normalized between 1 and -1. Thus, TdP-score ranges from 1 when all models are
223 predicted as high-risk or -1 when all models are predicted as low-risk.

224 Once the classifiers were built, both classifiers were tested using two different external
225 datasets: 1) the 16 validation CiPA drugs; 2) 81 drugs whose torasodgenic-risk was taken
226 from CredibleMeds [25]. CredibleMeds defines 4 TdP-risk categories, so in this work,
227 for the evaluation of the ternary classifiers, we considered: class 1 (“known risk of TdP”) as
228 high-risk; class 2 (“possible risk of TdP”) and class 3 (“conditional risk of TdP”) as
229 intermediate-risk; and class 4 (“no known risk of TdP”) as low-risk.

230 Finally, a feature selection algorithm was applied to reduce the number of needed
231 biomarkers. Specifically, a sequential forward floating search (SFFS) algorithm [26] was
232 used to identify the best subset of features differentiating the three TdP-risk categories. A
233 feature was considered as a certain biomarker, for example APD90, at the three different
234 concentrations. Therefore, the total number of biomarkers on which the SFFS algorithm
235 was applied was 9. In brief, starting from an empty set of features, the feature X_i that
236 maximizes the accuracy of the classifier when combined with the features Y_k that have
237 been previously selected, is added. After this forward step, SFFS performs backward

238 steps, removing features, provided that the objective function increases. A schematic
 239 representation of the algorithm is shown in **Figure 3**.

240 **Figure 3.** Schematic representation of the SFFS algorithm, based on Corino et al. [27].
 241 Each group of 9 bars represents the whole set of features, being a bar a feature. Each dark
 242 blue bar represents a chosen feature. Here, as an example, the algorithm starts with three
 243 features already selected that yield an accuracy $Acc(3)$. Then, in the Forward Selection
 244 block a new feature is added (colored in green) and the corresponding accuracy measured
 245 ($Acc(4)_i$). Not yet selected features are colored in light blue. The feature leading to the
 246 maximum accuracy is added to the selected set of features (purple bar). Following is the
 247 Backward Selection block, where each of the already selected features (except the last
 248 added) is removed (beige bar) from the set of selected features and the corresponding
 249 accuracy is computed ($Acc(3)_i$). If the maximum accuracy $Acc(3)_i$ is bigger than the first
 250 $Acc(3)$, then the feature is removed from the set of selected features. In case a feature is
 251 removed, Black Selection block is repeated, otherwise the next step is Forward Selection.
 252

253 Population of models parameter sets, the ORdmD CellML file and MATLAB code used
 254 in this work are available at: <https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/182593>

255 3 Results

256 3.1 Variability in drug response

257 The population of models produces electrophysiological variability when simulating
 258 drug effects. As shown in **Figure 4**, the same pharmacological intervention, in this case

259 10 times EFTPC of vandetanib (high TdP-risk drug), droperidol (intermediate TdP-risk
260 drug) or metoprolol (low TdP-risk drug), have very different effects throughout the
261 population of TorORd models. For example, in the case of vandetanib there are some
262 models, such as models number 32, 199, and 293, that prolong APD less than 40% with
263 respect to control conditions, while others prolong it more than 130% or even develop
264 repolarization abnormalities. These differences cannot be captured with the baseline
265 model.

266
267 **Figure 4.** Action potential traces of the calibrated population of models under vandetanib
268 effect, a high TdP-risk drug (red lines), under droperidol effect, an intermediate TdP-risk
269 drug (yellow lines) and metoprolol. Baseline model results for each drug are plotted in
270 black lines. The drug concentration is 10 times EFTPC.

271 Repolarization abnormalities observed across the simulations included early
272 afterdepolarizations and repolarization failure. No depolarization failure nor delay
273 afterdepolarizations were detected. Abnormalities in Ca^{2+} transient which did not affect
274 the action potential were not observed either.

275 The analysis of the population subgroups highlighted the ionic properties of those
276 models more prone to develop repolarization abnormalities under the effects of different
277 drugs. The most susceptible TorORd models presented significantly lower conductances
278 of I_{Kr} , and I_{Kb} , and higher conductances of I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} and I_{NCX} . **Figure 5** shows the mean

279 scaling factor values of the different ionic conductances for the TorORd-models
 280 developing repolarization abnormalities and the TorORd-models without repolarization
 281 abnormalities. This information could be useful to further investigate and establish
 282 clusters of patients in which the dose of proarrhythmogenic drugs should be avoided or
 283 reduced. For example, patients with cardiovascular pathologies, such as heart failure,
 284 hypertrophic cardiomyopathy or ischemic cardiopathy, undergo a ionic remodeling
 285 process in which conductances of I_{Kr} and I_{NaK} decrease and conductances of I_{CaL} and I_{NCX}
 286 increase [20,28,29], thus increasing their risk of suffering a drug-induced TdP. These
 287 patients require special attention in cardiac safety studies and high TdP-risk drugs should
 288 be administered with caution.

289

290 **Figure 5.** Mean scaling factor values of the different ionic conductances for the TorORd-
 291 models developing repolarization abnormalities (in red) and the TorORd-models without
 292 repolarization abnormalities (in green).

293 ORdmD-based simulations produced similar results. Individuals with greater
 294 probability of developing repolarization abnormalities also showed higher conductance
 295 values of I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{NCX} , and lower I_{Kr} . ORdmD-subpopulation did not show
 296 significant differences in terms of I_{Kb} . This may be explained because I_{Kb} conductance is
 297 more than 6 times higher in TorORd model, so its contribution to the AP is higher. On

298 the other hand, ORdmD-subpopulations show lower conductances of I_{Ks} and I_{NaK} . Mean
299 scaling factor values of the different ionic conductances for the ORdmD models
300 depending on the presence of repolarization abnormalities are shown in **Figure S4**.

301 **3.2 TdP-risk classifiers**

302 Next, the simulations of the 12 training CiPA drugs were used to train two TdP-risk
303 classifiers: one using the baseline model and the other classifier using the population of
304 models to account for electrophysiological variability. Then, the classification tool was
305 tested using two different external data sets: the 16 validation CiPA drugs and 81
306 CredibleMeds drugs.

307 Here we present the result of the simulations based on TorORd model, since it yields
308 slightly superior results than ORdmD. For the results of the simulations based on the
309 ORdmD model see the **Supplemental Materials (Tables S2 and S3, Figures S5 and**
310 **S6)**. Note, that the same methodology was followed for both AP models simulations
311 (TorORd and ORdmD).

312 **Figure 6** shows, for the 16 validation CiPA drugs, the percentage of models of the
313 TorORd population that the SVM classifies in each of the three TdP-risk categories. It
314 can be observed, that for some drugs as disopyramide, tamoxifen, or loratadine, the
315 different individuals of the population are assigned to the three TdP-risk categories. This
316 is due to electrophysiological variability.

317

318 **Figure 6.** Percentage of models predicted as high (red bar), intermediate (yellow bar), or
 319 low (green bar) TdP-risk for the 16 validation CiPA drugs using the SVM method on the
 320 TorORD population of models. High-risk CiPA drugs are represented at the top,
 321 intermediate CiPA drugs in the middle, and low-risk drugs at the bottom.

322 These percentages were the input for the logistic regression that predicts the overall
 323 TdP-risk class of the drug. The output of the logistic regression was summarized in the
 324 “TdP-score”. TdP-scores for the 16 CiPA validation drugs are shown in **Figure 7**. It can
 325 be seen that high-risk drugs have TdP-score values close to 1, intermediate-risk drugs
 326 take values close to 0, and low-risk drugs take values close to -1. The thresholds for
 327 separation between the three classes were determined in the training phase. For TorORD-
 328 population, the optimal threshold between high and intermediate-risk is 0.21 and the
 329 optimal threshold between intermediate and low-risk is -0.45. Out of the 16 drugs, 14 are
 330 correctly classified with this population-based classifier. The two misclassified drugs are:
 331 domperidone, an intermediate-risk drug, which is predicted as a high-risk drug; and
 332 tamoxifen, a low-risk drug, that is predicted as an intermediate-risk drug. When testing
 333 the classification tool with the 81-drug set from CredibleMeds, 16 drugs were
 334 misclassified. Namely, 3 high TdP-risk drugs (cilostazol, dronedarone an procainamide)
 335 were classified as intermediate risk drugs. Donepezil, a high TdP-risk drug, was

336 misclassified as a low TdP risk drug. From the intermediate TdP-risk drugs, lapatinib,
 337 nilotinib, paliperidone, sunitinib and tolterodine were predicted as high risk drugs; while
 338 desipramine, saquinavir, famotidine, propafenone and quetiapine were misclassified as
 339 low TdP-risk drugs. Finally, the low risk drugs cibenzoline and darunavir were
 340 misclassified as intermediate risk drugs.

341 TdP-scores representations for the 81 CredibleMeds drugs for both population of
 342 models (TorORd and ORdmD) are shown in **Figure S7 and S8**.

343
 344 **Figure 7.** TdP-score for the 16 CiPA validation drugs simulated on the TorORd
 345 population of models. Actual high-risk CiPA drugs are represented in red bars,
 346 intermediate-risk drugs in yellow and low-risk drugs in green. The dashed lines are the
 347 TdP-score threshold. Threshold1 is equal to 0.21 and all drugs with a higher TdP-score
 348 are predicted as high-risk. Threshold2 is equal to -0.45 and all drugs with a lower TdP-
 349 score are predicted as low-risk. TdP-score values comprised between both thresholds are
 350 considered as intermediate-risk.

351 The performance of the classifier using TorORd baseline model and the classifier using
 352 the population of TorORd models are shown in **Table 2**. The population-based classifier
 353 outperforms the baseline model-based classifier with both validation datasets. For both
 354 datasets, when using the population of models, the accuracy improves around 20
 355 percentual points and the mean classification error (MCE) is reduced to the half

356 approximately. In the case of the CiPA validation dataset, risperidone and droperidol
 357 (intermediate-risk drugs) and loratadine and droperidol (low-risk drugs) are classified
 358 correctly only if the population of models is used. In the case of the CredibleMeds data
 359 set, 7 high-risk, 2 intermediate-risk, and 7 low-risk drugs are misclassified if population
 360 of models is not considered. These results reflect the importance of taking into account
 361 electrophysiological variability when simulating the effects of drugs. Training and test
 362 accuracy of the different classifiers using the population of models are shown in
 363 **Supplementary Material, Table S5.**

364 **Table 2.** Confusion matrices and performance metrics (accuracy, mean classification
 365 error -MCE-, and Matthew correlation coefficient -MCC-) of the classifier using TorORD
 366 baseline model and the classifier using the population of TorORD models for both external
 367 validation datasets: the 16 CiPA drugs and for the 81 CredibleMeds drugs.

Baseline TorORD model							
<i>CiPA</i> <i>drugs</i>	High	Int.	Low	<i>CredibleMeds</i> <i>drugs</i>	High	Int.	Low
Pred. High	4	2	1	Pred. High	9	6	0
Pred. Int.	0	4	2	Pred. Int.	9	11	9
Pred. Low	0	1	2	Pred. Low	2	6	29
Accuracy:	62.5 %			Accuracy:	60.5 %		
MCE:	0.438			MCE:	0.420		
MCC:	0.456			MCC:	0.384		

368

Population of TorORD models							
<i>CiPA</i> <i>drugs</i>	High	Int.	Low	<i>CredibleMeds</i> <i>drugs</i>	High	Int.	Low
Pred. High	4	1	0	Pred. High	16	5	0
Pred. Int.	0	6	1	Pred. Int.	3	13	2
Pred. Low	0	0	4	Pred. Low	1	5	36
Accuracy:	87.5 %			Accuracy:	80.2 %		
MCE:	0.125			MCE:	0.210		
MCC:	0.813			MCC:	0.690		

369 Finally, a SFFS algorithm was applied to reduce the number of needed biomarkers.
 370 The minimum set of features that maximizes the accuracy of the classifier was the same
 371 for ORdmD and TorORD simulations. It was composed of: APD90, qNet, calcium

372 systolic concentration and the electromechanical window. A new classifier was trained
 373 again, this time using only these 4 features.

374 **Table 3** summarizes performance results of the new classifier that uses only 4 features
 375 extracted from a population of TorORd models. For the CiPA dataset, the classifier
 376 achieved the same accuracy (87.5%) than in the previous case, using all features. The two
 377 misclassified drugs are the same: domperidone and tamoxifen. However, when
 378 CredibleMeds data set is used the performance drops slightly. In this case, two more drugs
 379 (moxifloxacin - a high-risk drug- and fluvoxamine -an intermediate-risk drug) are
 380 misclassified (as intermediate-risk and as high-risk, respectively) thus reducing the
 381 accuracy in 2.4% and increasing MCE in 0.02. Despite this, it can be affirmed that the
 382 classifier continues to perform with considerable accuracy and that the 4 selected features
 383 are able to largely collect the torsadogenic effects of drugs.

384 **Table 3.** Confusion matrices and performance metrics (accuracy, mean classification
 385 error -MCE-, and Matthew correlation coefficient -MCC-) of the classifier based on the
 386 population of TorORd models, using as inputs: APD90, qNet, EMw, systolic $[Ca^{2+}]_i$.

Population of TorORd models							
<i>CiPA</i> <i>drugs</i>	High	Int.	Low	<i>CredibleMeds</i> <i>drugs</i>	High	Int.	Low
Pred. High	4	1	0	Pred. High	15	6	0
Pred. Int.	0	6	1	Pred. Int.	4	12	2
Pred. Low	0	0	4	Pred. Low	1	5	36
Accuracy:	87.5 %			Accuracy:	77.8 %		
MCE:	0.125			MCE:	0.235		
MCC:	0.813			MCC:	0.650		

387 Boxplots of the selected features, at 10 times the EFTPC, are represented in **Figure 8**.
 388 In general high-risk drugs greatly prolong APD90. qNet and the EMw follow a similar
 389 trend: high-risk drugs tend to decrease their value while low-risk drugs increase them.
 390 And regarding systolic calcium concentration, low-risk drugs especially reduce it. It can
 391 be observed that, individually, none of the features clearly discriminates between TdP-

392 risk classes, thus it is necessary to combine different biomarkers, and different
393 concentrations must be considered so that the classifier accurately performs.

394 **Figure 8.** Box plots of the 4 selected features (APD90, q_{net} , EMw, systolic Ca^{2+}) for at
 395 the 16 CiPA validation drugs simulated at 10 times the EFTPC on the population of
 396 TorORd models. The red-shaded area includes actual high-risk drugs, the yellow-shaded
 397 area the actual intermediate-risk drugs, and the green-shaded area the low-risk drugs.

398 4 Discussion

399 4.1 Main findings

400 In this work, we calibrated two population of models (TorORD and ORdmD) to account
401 for electrophysiological variability and we compared the performance of a ternary
402 classification tool, based on SVM, with and without electrophysiological variability.
403 These classifiers were blindly validated, as recommended by Li et al. [7], using the 16
404 validation CiPA drugs and an extra validation dataset composed of 81 drugs. Our main
405 findings are:

- 406 (i) Populations of models allowed to generate different AP responses under the
407 same pharmacological intervention and to identify ionic conductance profiles
408 more prone to develop TdP. We found that individuals with lower conductances
409 of I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , I_{NaK} , and I_{Kb} and higher conductances of I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{NCX} are more
410 prone to develop TdP.
- 411 (ii) Classification accuracy significantly improves (more than 20 percentual points)
412 when using population of models. This result highlights the benefits of using
413 population of models when predicting TdP-risk and suggest that considering
414 electrophysiological variability has the potential to improve *in silico* TdP-risk
415 assessment tools. Furthermore, the results are similar regardless of the
416 electrophysiological model used (ORdmJ or TorORD). The advantage of using
417 the population of models was also evidenced with the two test datasets used.
- 418 (iii) The feature selection algorithm SFSS revealed the 4 most relevant biomarkers
419 for the prediction of TdP out of the 9 biomarkers studied in this work. These
420 features were: APD90, qNet, systolic calcium concentration and EMw.

421 (iv) We have defined the TdP_score index, which provides a summarized
422 quantification of the TdP-risk. The most dangerous drugs take values close to 1
423 and the least dangerous close to -1.

424 **4.2 TdP-risk classifiers**

425 According to the levels of acceptable performance models defined by Li et al. [30] for
426 CiPA predictive models, the classification tool based on population of TorORd models,
427 which scored the highest performance in this work, presents an “excellent” performance
428 with a MCE lower than 0.3 with both validation datasets. Therefore, it can be said that
429 our models are acceptable for TdP-risk predictions.

430 Regarding the performance comparison of the classification tool, “General Principles”
431 for the validation of TdP-risk prediction models, published by Li’s group [7], suggest that
432 prediction models should differentiate between three TdP-risk categories and should be
433 validated with a hidden dataset. However, the authors are aware of only two papers that
434 have been published to date following this suggestion: a work by Li et al. [30], and a
435 recently published paper by Yoo [10]. Furthermore, these are not completely comparable
436 studies, as they do not take into account electrophysiological variability; they quantify
437 the uncertainty in pharmacological values and propagate it through the model. Li et al.
438 [30] proposed a logistic model using the *torsade metric score* (average of qNet across 1-
439 4xCmax). They accurately classified 12 drugs, missing disopyramide, domperidone,
440 clozapine, and risperidone. Yoo et al. [10] proposed an artificial neural network with 9
441 AP-related biomarkers. They also accurately classified 12 drugs out of the 16,
442 misclassifying disopyramide, azimilide, loratadine, and tamoxifen. As previously
443 mentioned, our classification tool misclassifies only 2 drugs out of the 16 CiPA validation
444 drugs (tamoxifen and domperidone) and 16 drugs out of the 81 CredibleMeds drug set.
445 As proposed by Li and colleagues [9], a plausible explanation for the misclassification of

446 these drugs might be technical difficulties for the characterization of drug potency, which
447 leads to mischaracterization of IC_{50} . Another reason for misclassification might be under
448 or overestimation of the role of a specific current of the in silico model, specifically poor
449 representation of the I_{NaL} and I_{CaL} inhibition or overrepresentation of I_{Kr} block effects [31].
450 This might be the case of tamoxifen, which shows similar potencies for I_{Kr} , I_{NaL} and I_{CaL} ,
451 but the effects captured by the in silico model on I_{CaL} and I_{NaL} seem insufficient to
452 counteract the prolongation of the action potential caused by I_{Kr} block. In addition, other
453 drug-related phenomena such as the effects on other pathways different than ionic
454 channels, trafficking inhibition, the activity of metabolites, or higher concentrations of
455 the compound in the cardiac tissue than in blood plasmas, may impact TdP-risk induction
456 but were not included in our work. These aspect could have favored the misclassification
457 of some drugs. As an example, donepezil prolongs QT interval by I_{Kr} block and also by
458 I_{Kr} trafficking inhibition [32]. Dronedarone is metabolized into N-debutyl-
459 dronedarone[33], a compound that retains up to one-third of the parent's activity. As both
460 have significant channel blocking effects, not considering N-debutyl-dronedarone
461 activity when simulating dronedarone might be the cause of its misclassification.
462 Cilostazol is a phosphodiesterase 3 (PED3) inhibitor that can favor the induction of TdP
463 because it induces intracellular cAMP elevation, which results in Ca^{2+} dynamic
464 disbalance, and early after depolarizations[34]. As for saquinavir, the underestimation of
465 its TdP-risk could be related to the of higher accumulation of the drug in myocardium
466 than in blood plasma [35], increasing the probability of provoking adverse effects in the
467 heart.

468 On the other hand, it should be noted that the ternary-classification tool presented here
469 achieves similar performance to previous TdP-risk assessment studies, where binary
470 classifications were carried out [13,22,24,29,36–40].

471 Furthermore, using populations of models allowed to identify ionic conductance
472 profiles more prone to develop TdP: individuals with lower conductances of I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , I_{NaK} ,
473 and I_{Kb} and higher conductances of I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{NCX} are more prone to develop TdP.
474 This is in closely agreement with other studies: Britton et al. [6] suggested that decreased
475 I_{NaK} , combined with low I_{Kr} , can increase proarrhythmic-risk of drugs; Passini's [29]
476 group showed that individuals with increased I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{NCX} and reduced I_{NaK} were
477 highly vulnerable to drug-induced repolarization abnormalities; Lacerda et al. [41] stated
478 that an enhancement of I_{NaL} plays a relevant role in increased risk of TdP. This
479 information may provide insight about clusters of patients in which the dose of
480 proarrhythmogenic drugs should be avoided or reduced. In fact, this ionic profile is
481 consistent with different conditions or situations that have been associated with an
482 increased incidence of TdP. For example, women, who have higher risk to develop TdP,
483 present lower I_{Kr} , and I_{Ks} [42,43]; or patients with chronic systemic inflammation, which
484 can exacerbate drugs' cardiotoxic effects, have a lower expression of I_{Kr} and a higher
485 expression of I_{CaL} [29]. The utility of population of models to represent
486 electrophysiological variability in *in silico* studies was first introduced by Sobie [45];
487 since then different publications have employed this strategy [24,46–48]. The application
488 of the population of *in silico* models approach is reviewed in [5].

489 **4.3 Limitations of the study**

490 As mentioned in the previous section, one the limitation of this work is the reliability
491 of pharmacological data (IC_{50} , h and EFTPC). Recently, efforts have been made to
492 standardize experimental protocols and increase model prediction accuracy
493 standardization protocols [49,50]. However, these new experimental data are only
494 available for a few drugs. To deal with it, we used a similar approach to previous studies
495 [13,22]: we reduced source variability by considering data from similar experimental

496 conditions and then assumed that the published data represented a distribution of values
497 affected by a random error and the variability due to the experimental conditions. Then,
498 the most representative value considering variability was the median, as it is a robust
499 estimator of the central tendency of a data set. In addition, the present results could be
500 extended in the future by combining the uncertainty quantification in the pharmacological
501 data with the population of models to better understand model's tolerability to input
502 variability. Previous works [51–53] have incorporated methods for quantifying
503 uncertainty in pharmacological data (IC50s and hill coefficients) into the CiPA
504 framework and have demonstrated that they provide valuable information, which can
505 inform in the proarrhythmic evaluation of drugs. Furthermore, if more data on
506 pharmacological hERG binding kinetics were available, it would also be of high interest
507 to simulate drug effects with hERG binding kinetics data, since it could improve the
508 classification performance, as some previous studies have shown [30,54].

509 Another limitation is the dependence of the populations results on the number of models
510 and on the distribution of probability from where the scaling factors are sampled. Here,
511 we consider that an initial population of 1,000 models provides a good balance between
512 having an adequate sample size and avoiding having very similar models that just
513 contribute to increase simulation time. In this sense, we repeated the methodology for
514 building the classifiers but starting from a population of 5,000 initial models in order to
515 study if classification results were convergent. For both populations of models (ORdmJ
516 and TorORD), we found that the final drug classification (based on the TdP-score) was
517 the same with the population of 5,000 models and with the population of 1,000 models,
518 although the percentage of models in each category was slightly different. The
519 distributions of the biomarkers used for the calibration across each population (TorORD
520 and ORdmD) with 5,000 initial models, can be consulted in the **Supplementary**

521 **Material, Figures S9 and S10.** Furthermore, comparison between the classification
522 results for the 16 CiPA drugs when using an initial population of 5,000 TorORd models
523 or an initial 1,000 TorORd models is shown in **Supplementary Material, Table S6.** On
524 the other hand, we chose a normal distribution since the aim of the study was to predict
525 drugs effects in a healthy population, where ionic conductances are supposed to be a
526 continuum of values normally distributed. In addition, population variability was
527 considered only in ionic current conductances because it constitutes the major
528 determinant behind physiological variability [55]. Another limitation is precisely that
529 drug effects were only simulated on healthy cardiomyocytes, and the incidence of TdP is
530 known to be very rare in this population.

531 It is worth noting that the methodology used here does not seek for the identifiability
532 of the ion channel conductances. Therefore, the scaling factors in the populations of
533 models do not necessarily represent the real variation of ionic conductances responsible
534 for experimentally observed AP. Different strategies for the identifiability of the
535 parameters of the AP model are presented in the review by Whittaker and colleagues [56].

536 On the other hand, regarding the rate dependence, in this study we performed
537 simulations at an intermediate and physiological-like heart rate (60 beats per minutes) as
538 a first approximation. The study of the performance dependence on the stimulation rate
539 could help refine the classification tool. According to some authors, the best
540 discrimination between TdP-risk categories is achieved at stimulations of 1Hz [37,57];
541 instead, Dutta and colleagues observed the best category separation at slower rates (0.5
542 Hz) [54]; while other authors have not found any rate dependence in their classification
543 results [22].

544 Another limitation of this work is the strong dependence of classification performance
545 on the information taken as reference. Here, for the validation drugs not included in the
546 CiPA reference list we used the CredibleMeds database [25]. Although it is a well
547 recognized database which feeds from clinical data, it mixes the QT prolongation and the
548 TdP risk end points. QT prolongation is closely related to but distinct from TdP end point,
549 and inferring TdP risk only from QT interval is inaccurate[7]. In this sense, CredibleMeds
550 class 2 (“possible risk of TdP”), which here was considered as intermediate risk of TdP
551 for the classifiers development, includes compounds that can cause QT prolongation in
552 the absence of evidence for a risk of TdP. Therefore, some of the CredibleMeds validation
553 drugs in the intermediate TdP-risk class actually might have no known risk of TdP and
554 should have been considered as low TdP-risk instead. This could explain the lower
555 performance among all the classifiers when validated with the CredibleMeds dataset.

556 It is to be noted that our simulations do not consider other pharmacological aspects such
557 as drug interactions, effects of active metabolites or accumulation of drugs in cardiac
558 tissues, etc.

559 **5 Conclusions**

560 In this work, we developed a ternary-classification tool based on population of models
561 for the assessment of drug-induced TdP. This tool quantifies the percentage of models in
562 which the drug will be dangerous and summarizes the risk of TdP in the biomarker “TdP
563 score”. The validation of the classification tool with two different “hidden” drug sets
564 showed that its performance was higher than when just using the baseline model.
565 Simulations with population of models also allowed the identification of individuals
566 which are more prone to develop TdP. Taken together, the results outline the benefits of
567 using population of models when predicting TdP-risk and suggest that considering

568 electrophysiological variability has the potential to improve *in silico* TdP-risk assessment
569 tools.

570 The methodology presented in this study provides new opportunities to assess drug-
571 induced TdP, taking into account electrophysiological variability. The use of such *in silico*
572 tools as screening methods could be helpful to accelerate the development of new drugs
573 and reduce the costs of cardiac safety screening in preclinical phases.

574 **6 Abbreviations used**

575 AP, action potential; APD_x; action potential duration at x% of the repolarization; BCL,
576 basic length cycle; EAD, early after depolarization; EFTPC, effective free therapeutic
577 plasma concentration (peak); EM_w, electromechanical window; IC₅₀, half-maximal
578 inhibitory concentration; MCE, mean classification error; MCC, Mathews correlation
579 coefficient; SVM, support vector machines; TdP, Torsade de Pointes.

580 **7 Conflict of interest statement**

581 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial
582 or financial relationships.

583 **8 Author Contributions**

584 JL contributed to the design of the study, performed the simulations, analyzed results
585 and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. BT and JS contributed to the design of the
586 study, analyzed the results and supervised the project. All authors contributed to
587 manuscript revision, read and approved the submitted version.

588

589

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598 **10 Appendix**

599 Population of models parameter sets, the ORdmD CellML file and MATLAB code used
600 in this work are available at: <https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/182593>

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